

Detection and molecular analysis of grapevine virus A (GVA) in vineyards of Azerbaijan

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Concurrent Grapevine virus A (GVA) infection with other grapevine viruses can complicate disease diagnosis and management. To investigate the occurrence of GVA, 48 samples exhibiting virus-like symptoms such as leaf yellowing, reddening, fan leaf, mosaic, leaf rolling, and shortening of internodes were collected from 18 commercial vineyards in Azerbaijan during the 2019-2022 growing seasons. Phloem scrapings were analyzed using DAS-ELISA and RT-PCR. RT-PCR was conducted using specific primers for GVA to amplify a portion of the coat protein gene (CP) from synthesized cDNA obtained from total RNA extracted from the samples. Amplicons of the expected size of 272 bp were obtained for the mentioned viruses (but not from healthy samples). GVA was detected in 4 out of 48 samples, resulting in an incidence rate of approximately 8.3% (1/12). The results of this study may facilitate the development of management approaches for grapevine viruses in grape-growing areas of Azerbaijan.

Keywords: Grapevine viruses, survey, detection, ELISA, RT-PCR, GVA

INTRODUCTION

Grapevine (*Vitis* spp.) is an important fruit crop that has been cultivated for thousands of years for its fruit, which is used to produce wine, juice, raisins, and table grapes. It is a valuable commodity in the global agricultural industry, with the top producers being Italy, France, and Spain, as well as in our country. Grapevine production in Azerbaijan has a long history and is an important part of the country's agriculture (Bayramova et al., 2021). The unique geographical and climatic conditions of the region, particularly in the foothills of the Caucasus Mountains, create favorable conditions for grapevine cultivation. Azerbaijan is known for producing high-quality wine and table grapes, with some of the most popular grape varieties being Bayan Shira, Madrasa, Mahmudu, and Saperavi. The country has over 60 grape varieties that are grown for both local consumption and export, with the majority of grapevine production taking place in the regions of Ganja-Gazakh, Absheron, and Shirvan. Grapevine viruses pose a significant threat to the grapevine industry, with the potential to cause significant economic losses to grape growers and winemakers (Sultanova et al., 2019). The viruses can reduce yields, affect fruit quality, and decrease the longevity of the vineyard. There are many different types of grapevine viruses,

including *Grapevine fanleaf virus*, *Grapevine leafroll-associated virus*, *Grapevine fleck virus*, and *Grapevine virus A*, among others (Diaz-Lara et al., 2023). These viruses can cause various symptoms such as yellowing, mosaic patterns on leaves, stunted growth, and shortened internodes, which can be mistaken for nutrient deficiencies or other diseases. *Grapevine virus A* (GVA) is a significant threat to grapevine production due to its ability to spread rapidly, causing yield losses and reducing the longevity of vineyards, with no effective cure or control measures currently available (Osman et al., 2013). *Grapevine virus A* (GVA) belongs to the genus *Vitivirus*, in the family *Betaflexiviridae*, which is a group of single-stranded RNA viruses that infect grapevine plants. Other members of this genus include *Grapevine virus B* (GVB), *Grapevine virus D* (GVD), and *Grapevine virus E* (GVE). GVA has a conserved genome organization, a genome size of approximately 7.2 kilobases, which encodes a polyprotein that is subsequently cleaved to form functional proteins, which encodes for at least four proteins and shares significant genetic similarity with other members of the *Vitivirus* genus. This virus is transmitted in a non-persistent manner by several species of mealybugs, including *Planococcus ficus* and *Pseudococcus longispinus*. Simultaneous infection of GVA with other grapevine viruses can make the diagnosis and

management of the disease more challenging. Molecular characterization of GVA involves studying the genetic material of the virus to identify and analyze its components. The coat protein (CP) gene, responsible for forming the capsid that encapsulates the virus, is one of the most studied genes in GVA molecular characterization.

The aim of the study was to investigate the sanitary status of GVA in commercial vineyards in Azerbaijan.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant material

In this study, the presence and spread of *Grapevine virus A* (GVA) in various commercial vineyards across seven regions including Absheron, Salyan, Jalilabad, Masalli, Lankaran, Shamakhi, and Ganja in Azerbaijan were investigated. A total of 48 grapevine samples from 18 commercial vineyards, including different grapevine cultivars, were screened for GVA detection using both serological (DAS-ELISA) and molecular (RT-PCR) analyses. Samples were collected from grapevines that displayed symptoms indicative of virus infection, including leaf mosaic, rolling, yellowing or reddening, vein banding, and internode shortening. The collected leaf samples were transported to the laboratory and stored at 4°C until they were processed further.

Double-antibody sandwich Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (DAS-ELISA)

To detect the possible presence of the *Grapevine virus A* DAS-ELISA was performed using antisera against GVA developed by Bioreba AG (Reinach, Switzerland) following the manufacturer's instructions. For the ELISA tests, all buffers were prepared according to the instructions provided. Grapevine leaf samples were homogenized (1:5 W/V) in Tris extraction buffer using a sterile mortar and pestle, and 100 µl of the extracts were incubated overnight at 4°C in microtiter plate wells that had been treated with a 100 µl of 1:1000 dilution of GVA-IgG in carbonate coating buffer. The microtiter plate wells were rinsed with washing buffer and then incubated with 100 µl of alkaline phosphatase-conjugated IgG diluted 1:1000 in conjugate buffer (3 hours at 37°C). The wells were washed and incubated with 100 µl of substrate for 1 hour at room temperature, and the absorbance was measured at 405 nm using a microtiter plate reader (Stat Fax Microplate, Awareness Technology, USA). All samples were tested twice, and the results were considered positive if the mean absorbance was greater than or equal to three times the average reading of negative

(healthy) controls. Alternatively, the presence of the viruses was confirmed using RT-PCR.

RNA extraction

The CTAB method described by Sambrook et al. (1989) with minor modifications was used to extract total RNA from 200 mg of scraped bark tissue from basal nodes, petioles, and/or midribs. Similarly, 200 mg of leaf tissue was added to pre-warmed 2 ml of extraction buffer containing 4 µl of β-mercaptoethanol in a sterile extraction bag. The sample extracts were incubated at 60°C for 15 minutes with intermittent vortexing, followed by the addition of an equal volume of chloroform: isoamyl alcohol (24:1). The mixture was vortexed for 10 minutes and centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 10 minutes at 4°C. RNA was precipitated by adding 1/3 volume of 7.5 M lithium chloride (LiCl) and incubating the samples on the ice at 4°C overnight, followed by centrifugation at 8000 rpm for 30 minutes at 4°C. The pellet was resuspended in 100 µl of DEPC-treated water, 0.2 volume of 2M sodium acetate (pH 5.2), and 2 volumes of 100% ethanol. The tubes were then incubated at -20°C for 2 hours and centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 10 minutes. After discarding the supernatant, the pellet was washed with 70% ethanol, and the extracted RNA was stored at -20°C or -80°C for further use. The concentration and purity of RNA were determined by spectrophotometric analysis at 230, 260, and 280 nm wavelengths and the ratios of A260/A280 and A260/A230 were calculated. Additionally, the RNA quality was evaluated using 1% agarose gel electrophoresis, followed by staining with ethidium bromide and visualization under UV light.

Reverse transcription-polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR)

RT-PCR was performed using virus-specific primers GVA-F/GVA-R (GAGGTAGATATAGTAGGAC CTA (a), TCGAACATAACCTGTGGCTC (s)) according to Goszczynski and Jooste, 2003, in two steps. To synthesize the complementary strand, 2 µl of extracted RNA was submitted to reverse transcription in a final volume of 20 µl, using 2µl RT buffer 10x (0.5 M Tris-HCl, 0.7 M KCl, 0.1 M MgCl₂, pH 8), 1µl DTT (100 mol/µl), 1µl dNTPs (10mmol/ µl), 0.5 µl RNase inhibitor (10 mmol/µl) and 2 µl Reverse primer (100 pmol/µl) for one hour at 47°C with 0.5 µl MMuLV reverse transcriptase (200 U/µl). To perform PCR, 5 µl of the RT reactions were utilized, and the PCR reaction was conducted in a final volume of 20 µl, consisting of 20 ng cDNA, 10 mM of each dNTP (Solis BioDyne, Estonia), 1.6 mM MgCl₂, 1U of Taq DNA polymerase (Solis BioDyne, Estonia), 0.5 µl of each primer pair (10 pmol/µl), and 1X PCR buffer.

Thermal cycling was executed using a SimpliAmp Thermal Cycler (Applied Biosystems, USA), and the PCR products were preserved at 4°C or -20°C and examined by electrophoresis in a 1.5 % agarose gel with 1X Tris-Borate EDTA buffer (TBE) and stained with ethidium bromide (EB). DNA bands were visualized using the UV-Gel Doc system (UK), and the molecular weight of the PCR products was approximated using a 2-Log DNA Ladder (NEB, UK).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the entire survey period, typical symptoms such as interveinal discoloration, redness, chlorosis, and downward leaf rolling were observed on both red and white grapevine cultivars (Fig. 1). No significant difference was observed in the occurrence of leaf curling symptoms between regions and fields based on visual assessment.

Our research based on serological tests revealed that one out of the eight grapevine cultivars analyzed were positive for GVA, with a total of 4 out of 48 samples (8.3%) confirmed to be infected. The “Separavi” cultivar showed a higher incidence of infection, while no infection was detected in all other cultivars throughout the entire study. To further validate the serological test results, molecular analyses (RT-PCR and PCR) were carried out. The obtained RNA was used as a template in RT-PCR, and PCR was performed by using GVA-specific primer pair GVA-F/GVA-R, which amplifies a 272 bp fragment that encompasses part of the coat protein (CP) gene coding region (Fig. 2). In instances where DAS-ELISA failed to produce positive results, positive signals were detected with RT-PCR testing. The PCR products were electrophoresed on a 1.5% agarose gel containing ethidium bromide (0.5g/ml), and their expected sizes were determined by

comparing them to a 2-Log DNA Ladder from NEB. The gel was visualized under a UV transilluminator, and images were captured using a Gel documentation system from England, UK.

Overall, this research verified the presence of GVA on grapevines in southern Azerbaijan (Jalilabad, Masalli), using DAS-ELISA tests and molecular detection via RT-PCR with specific primers. Such infection rate is low in comparison with the sanitary status of Italian cultivars – 8% (Caruso et al., 2022), grapevines in Turkey – 53% (Balsak et al., 2021) or Tunisia – 63% (Selmi et al., 2018). *Grapevine virus A* is a widely distributed virus that infects grapevines worldwide. It is one of the most common grapevine viruses and is responsible for significant economic losses in the grape industry. The virus is primarily transmitted by mealybugs, although other insect vectors such as aphids and scale insects can also transmit the virus. GVA has been reported in various grape-growing regions around the world, including Europe, North America, South America, Asia, Africa, and Australia. In Europe, GVA has been reported in countries such as France, Italy, Spain, and Portugal (Caruso et al., 2022). In North America, GVA has been detected in California, Oregon, and Washington states, among others (Martin et al., 2005; Alabi et al., 2014). In South America, the virus has been reported in Chile (Fiore et al., 2008) and Argentina (Rivadeneira et al., 2022; Gomez Talquenca et al., 2023), while in Asia, GVA has been detected in China (Pio Ribeiro et al., 2004), Iran (Moradi et al., 2017), and Turkey (Çiftçi et al., 2015). GVA was also detected during phytosanitary monitoring of Russian commercial vineyards in the Krasnodar, Stavropol, and the Republic of Crimea (Porotikova et al., 2021). In Africa, GVA has been reported in South Africa (Engelbrecht and Kasdorf, 2017) and Egypt (Fattouh et al., 2014), and in Australia (Wu et al., 2020), the virus has been detected in grapevines grown in various states.

Fig. 1. The GVA symptoms observed included mild chlorosis, leaf rolling downwards, internodes shortening, and interveinal discoloration characterized by reddening and chlorosis.

Fig. 2. Agarose gel electrophoresis showing results of RT-PCR detection of GVA using primer pairs GVA-F/GVA-R. Total RNA was isolated from juvenile leaves (A) obtained from 48 distinct grapevines, and the expected length of the amplified fragment was 272 bp (B). Line: M –marker (2-Log DNA Ladder (NEB, UK)), 1 and 2- healthy samples, 3- positive samples. RNA and RT-PCR products were separated in 1.5 % agarose gel.

This study is the initial survey report of the existence of *Grapevine virus A* in Azerbaijan's regions, which enhances our understanding of preserving the sanitary conditions of commercial vineyards in our country. Due to its wide distribution and significant impact on grapevine health and productivity, GVA is a major concern for grape growers worldwide, and measures are being taken to prevent its spread and manage its effects on vineyards. The results of the study could help vineyard owners and managers identify potential problems and take steps to prevent or control them, ultimately leading to healthier and more productive grapevines and a better yield of high-quality grapes.

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Azərbaycanda üzüm bağlarında üzümün A virusunun (GVA) deteksiyası və molekulyar analizi

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Üzümün A virusunun digər üzüm virusları ilə eyni vaxtda yoluxması xəstəliyin diaqnozunu və idarə edilməsini çətinləşdirə bilər. GVA-nın Azərbaycanda yayılmasını araşdırmaq üçün 2019-2022-ci illərdə üzümün vegetasiya mövsümlərində 18 fərdi üzüm bağından yarpaqlarda saralma, qızartı, yarpağın aşağıya doğru bükülməsi, mozaika, yarpaq burulması və düyünlərarası məsafənin qısalması kimi virusa bənzər simptomlara malik 48 bitki nümunəsi toplanmışdır. Yarpaqdan ayrılmış floem hissə DAS-ELISA və RT-PCR metodlarından istifadə etməklə tədqiq edilmişdir. Nümunələrdən ekstraksiya edilmiş total RNT-dən sintez edilmiş kDNT-dən örtük protein geninin (CP) bir hissəsini amplifikasiya etmək üçün GVA genomu üçün gen spesifik praymerlərdən istifadə etməklə RT-PCR aparılmışdır. Qeyd olunan virus üçün gözlənilən ölçüdə 272 bp olan ampikonlar əldə edilmişdir (sağlam nümunələrdə aşkar edilməmişdir). Beləliklə GVA virusu 48 nümunədən 4-də aşkar edilmişdir və yayılma dərəcəsi təxminən 8,3% (1/12) təşkil etmişdir. Bu tədqiqatın nəticələri Azərbaycanın üzümçülük ərazilərində üzüm viruslarının idarə olunması istiqamətində inteqrativ yanaşmaların işlənilib hazırlanmasına kömək edə bilər.

Açar sözlər: Üzüm virusları, monitoring, deteksiya, ELISA, RT-PCR, GVA